

MATHEMATICS

ON SOME WAYS FOR CALCULATION DEFINITE INTEGRALS

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Abstract

One of the classical problems is the calculation of the definite integrals. The specialists encounter very often the calculation of definite integrals. Traditionally, to calculate some definite integrals were used integral sums as the rectangular method, trapezoid and Simpson methods etc. By using that all methods have their own advantages and disadvantages. Currently, experts are trying to construct more accurate methods with the improved properties. Therefore, construction of methods with the improved properties is always relevant. Following what was said, here is a suggestion for a new way for calculation of definite integral. For this aim offered here to use the some relationship between the both ODEs and definite integral. And suggested to use the intersection of definite integrals with the initial-value problem for the Ordinary Differential Equations. In the first time this idea was used by Euler in the result of which appeared Euler's explicit method. Here, this idea has been generalized and has constructed more general methods for the calculation of definite integrals. And the advantages of these methods were also shown. The advantages of the suggested methods here have been illustrated by using some simple examples.

Keywords. Initial-value problem for ODEs, definite integral, stability and degree, advanced and multistep methods, methods with the fractional step-size.

Introduction.

With the calculation of the definite integrals the specialists have met in the investigation of the orbit of the selection body, by taking into account that the orbit of these bodies are described by using ODEs. Therefore, many scientists have studied the initial-value problem for the ODEs. Many famous scientists, such as Newton, Cattes, Euler, V.I. Krilov, Simpson, Adams, Sobolev, R. Aliyev, Bakhalov, Imanova, Ibrahimov and etc. have studied this problem. Some of them have constructed methods for calculation of definite integrals and others have suggested some ways for constructing the methods with the new properties. Here both directions are used to calculate the definite integral (see for example [1]-[7]). And also used comparison of the proposed here, methods with the known.

Let us to consider the following definite integral:

$$y(b) = \int_a^b f(x)dx, \quad (1)$$

the continues function $f(x)$ -is define on the segment $[a,b]$. For the calculation of the integral (1), let us to devote the segment $[a,b]$ into N -equal part by the mesh-points $x_{i+1} = x_i + h$ ($i = 0,1,\dots,N$). In usually the integral (1) is calculated by some quadrature formula, which can be presented as follows(see for example [8]-[12]):

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx = h \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_i f_i + R_n, \quad (2)$$

here R_n -is reminder term β_i ($i = 0,1,\dots,N$) are the coefficients of the formula (2) and real numbers,

$x_0=a$ and $x_N=b$. In usually for the construction of quadrature formula considered the case $N = mk$, here m -is the amount of the subintervals, but k -amount of the mesh-points, participated in the construction of the method of type (2). For example, if $N = mk$, then for the calculation of integral one can constructed the following method:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_N} f(x)dx = \sum_{i=1}^m \int_{x_{(i-1)k}}^{x_{ik}} f(x)dx, \quad (3)$$

By using some quadrature formula in the equality of (3) one can write:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_N} f(x)dx \approx h \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j f(x_{i+j}). \quad (4)$$

It is obvious that in different segments the coefficients can be taken differently. In this case formula (4) can be written as follows:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_N} f(x)dx = h \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j^{(i)} f(x_{i+j}). \quad (5)$$

One can easily understand that, when using the method (5), the question arises: when the errors obtained in the application of the method (5) be limited?

The answer to this question can be found in the following section.

§1. On the estimation of the errors receiving in using formula (5).

For the investigation of the errors, which arises in the application of multistep method to calculation of the definite integrals, let us to consider the following equality(see for example [13]-[17]):

$$y(x) - y(x_0) = \int_{x_0}^x y'(s) ds. \quad (6)$$

Let us to consider the following initial problem:

$$y'(x) = g(x, y), \quad y(x_0) = y_0, \quad x_0 \leq x \leq X.$$

If to use the equality (6) in ordinary differential equation, then receive the following:

$$y(x) = y(x_0) + \int_{x_0}^x g(s, y(s)) ds. \quad (8)$$

It is easy to understand that the integral equation (8) and initial-value problem (7) are equivalent. And also it is known that for the numerical solution of problem (1), one of the suitable method is the multistep method, which can be presented as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i y_{n+i} = h \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i g_{n+i}, \quad (9)$$

here $g_m = g(x_m, y_m)$, $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

Suppose that the continuous solution of problem (7) has defined on the segment $[x_0, X]$, but the function $g(x, y)$ has defined in some closed set and there has the continuous partial derivatives up to p , inclusively. And also have used here some denotation, for example, y_i is the approximately values of the solution of the problem (7) and $y(x_i)$ is the corresponding exact values. The mesh-points are denoted by the $x_{i+1} = x_i + h$, here $h > 0$ is the step-size. It should be noted that Multistep method applied to the calculation of the definite integrals turns into the following form:

$$y_{n+k} = y_n + h \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i g_{n+i}, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - k. \quad (10)$$

As is known for the convergence of the method (9), it's stability is necessary and sufficient (see for example [18]-[25]).

Definition 1. Method (9) called as the stable if the roots of the following polynomial $\rho(\lambda) = \alpha_k \lambda^k + \alpha_{k-1} \lambda^{k-1} + \dots + \alpha_1 \lambda + \alpha_0$ located in the unit circle on the boundary of which there is not multiply root.

Noted that, for the comparison of the numerical methods in often are used the conception of degree, which can be defined as follows.

Definition 2. The integer value p called as the degree for the method (9), if the following takes place:

$$\sum_{i=0}^k (\alpha_i y(x+ih) - h \beta_i y'(x+ih)) = O(h^{p+1}), \quad h \rightarrow 0. \quad (11)$$

It is not difficult to show that, method (10) is stable. The characteristics polynomial $\rho(\lambda)$ of the method (10) can be presented as follows:

$$\lambda^k - 1 = 0. \quad (12)$$

All the roots of this equation are on the unit circle and differ from each others, because method (10) is stable. Noted that method (10) remembers of Adams methods, but they are not one and the same. And it is easy to understand that in the set of roots of the equation (12) in a complex roots are always presents for the

$k \geq 3$ absolute values for which are equal to one, therefore method (10) is stable. The coefficients of the method (10) satisfies the conditions imposed on the coefficients of the method (9), which fundamentally has investigated by Dahlquist. The named conditions can be presented as follows:

A. The coefficients $\alpha_i, \beta_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, k)$ some real number and $\alpha_k \neq 0$.

B. The characteristic polynomials:

$$\rho(\lambda) \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i \lambda^i, \quad \nu(\lambda) \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i \lambda^i,$$

have not common factor different from constant.

C. $\delta(1) \neq 0$ and $p \geq 1$.

It is clear that the method (10) can be received from the method (9) as the partial case, but in the construction of some methods the coefficients $\alpha_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, k)$ is selected so that, the polynomial $\rho(\lambda)$ does not have complex roots. Hence the preferred use of method (9) in solving many applied problems. Therefore, let us consider application of the method (9) to calculation of definite integrals.

§2. Application of the method (9) to calculation of definite integral (1).

Noted that the volume of the computational work in the application of the method (10) to calculation of definite integrals by using equality of (5) will be less than errors, receiving in using of the method (9). But method (9) is more general, than the method (10) and therefore one can be constructed the new multistep methods with the new properties, which can provide a reduction in error when using method. For this, let us to consider application of the method (9) to calculation of definite integral (1). For this, here proposed to use equalities (6)-(8). By using relationship between of these equalities, one can be applied method (9) to calculation of definite integral (1). In first, let us to solve problem (7) to use explicit Euler method. In this case receive:

$$y_{i+1} = y_i + hg(x_i, y_i). \quad (13)$$

It is clear that in the calculation of the value y_{i+1} by the method (13) are not arises any difficult. But if the method (13) to change by the following method:

$$y_{i+1} = y_i + hg(x_{i+1}, y_{i+1}), \quad (14)$$

then in the application of this method, arise some difficulties, which related with the solving of nonlinear algebraic equations (see for example [26]-[30]). Difficulty of this problem in using of this method is due to the fact that this method is implicit. If the function $g(x, y)$ is depending of $y (g(x, y) = f(x))$, then above noted defect will not occur. It follows from here that, if we applied method (9) to calculation of the integral (1), then are not arises above mentioned difficulties. Thus receive that $y_N = y_b$. Many specialists proposed constructed more accurate methods for calculating of the integral (1), in the results of which appeared the new methods that used the higher derivatives of the

function of $f(x)$ in the application of calculating of definite integral (1). Some authors have suggested using the calculating function, which is written under the integral sign. For example methods of Gauss, Chebishev, Ibrahimov, Imanova and etc. (see for example [31]-

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(x_{n+1/2}); y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_n) + 3f(x_{n+2/3}))/4, \quad (15)$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_{n+1}) + 3f(x_{n+1/3}))/4, y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_{n+1/2+\alpha}) + f(x_{n+1/2-\alpha}))/2, \alpha = \sqrt{3}/6. \quad (16)$$

And now let us to consider comparison of these methods. The first method in (15) is the midpoint method which is explicit, stable and has the degree of $p=2$. As is known if in the method of (9) to put $k=1$, then one can be constructed explicit and stable method with the degree $P_{\max} = 1$, which can be presented as follows:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_n)), R_n = \frac{h^2}{2} y''(x_n) + O(h^3).$$

If to compares midpoint and explicit Euler methods, then receive that in the application of the midpoint method arises difficult related calculation of the value $y_{n+1/2}$. However, one can be freed from this disadvantages by using replacement h by $2h$, in this case receive the following method:

$$y_{n+2} = y_n + 2hf(x_{n+1}), \quad (18)$$

which is usually called as the two-step method. This method is stable and has the degree $p=2$. Noted that this result to corresponding Dahlquist's law. The second method of (15) is the hybrid method, which is stable has the degree $p=3$. And in this method participate the values of the solution of the problem (8) at the 3 (three) points, but in second method at the 4 (forth) points. Noted that the first method in the (16) also has used information about of the solution our problems at the 4 (fourth) points. Thus receive that the methods in the (16) are used the same value of information about the solution of the solved problem. But the first method in (16) has the degree $p=3$, and the second method has the degree of $p=4$. If to comprise methods (15) and (16) by taking into account they degree, then receive that the second method in the (16) is best. Noted that the second method in (15) is explicit, but the first method in (16) is implicit. By using these methods one can be constructed predictor-corrector methods. However, the best combination of these methods is to find the half-sum above mentioned methods, which will be more exact than the results receiving by using the second

[36]). Here by the continue of these ways have recommending to use the hybrid methods. For the shown the advantages of these methods, let us to consider the following methods:

method in (15) and the first method (16). These methods are bilateral or two-sided. Therefore the value receiving by using half-sum of these methods are more exact. Thus, here have constructed the 4(four) methods and have given some ways for it's application to solve some problems. Noted that by using above described sequences of operations one can constructed step by step algorithm for solving problem(1). Similar research has been carried out with many authors (see for example [37]-[41]). For the illustration of the receiving here results, let us consider to the following section.

Numerical results.

There are some ways for solving above named question. One of these way is the using some tables for the tabulated and comparison the receiving results. It should be noted that this method for the comparison of the receiving results are more clear. Let us consider to solve following simple example:

$$y' = \cos(x), y(0) = 0, x \in [0,1], \text{ The exact}$$

solution for which is $y(x) = \sin(x)$.

Noted that one of the known method for calculation of definite integrals is the Simpson

method, which can be presented as:

$$y_{n+2} = y_n + h(y'_{n+2} + 4y'_{n+1} + y'_n)/3. \quad (19)$$

By using methods with the fractional step-size receive more perspective methods. For the illustration of this let us to write method of (19) in the following form:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(y'_{n+1} + 4y'_{n+1/2} + y'_n)/6. \quad (20)$$

This method is stable and has the degree $p=4$, which can be comparison with the methods (15) and (16). Let us remember that for receiving an acceptable result in usually are use the reducing (decreasing) of the step size. By using this idea, here has considered application of the Simpson method to calculation of integral (1) with the step size of h and $h/2$. Results have been tabulated in the Table 1.

Table 1.

Receiving results for step size $h = 0.1$

Step size	Variable	Error for the method (19)	Error for the method (20)
$h = 0.1$	0.2	0.11E-06	0.69E-08
	0.3	0.10E-06	0.10E-07
	0.4	0.21E-06	0.13E-07
	0.5	0.21E-06	0.16E-07
	0.6	0.31E-06	0.19E-07
	0.7	0.30E-06	0.22E-07
	0.8	0.39E-06	0.24E-07
	0.9	0.38E-06	0.27E-07
	1.0	0.46E-06	0.29E-07

The receiving results here correspond to the theoretical. It is not difficult to understand that the hybrid methods are more exact than the implicit methods of multistep types. And methods given by using derivatives of the required solutions can be applied to solve

$$y' = (4 \exp(-y) - x^3) / 3 + \frac{4}{3} \int_1^x \frac{s^2}{x} \exp(y(s)) ds, \quad 1 \leq x \leq 2, \quad y(1) = 0, \quad 1 \leq x \leq 2. \quad (21)$$

Exact solution for this problem can presented as: $y(x) = \ln x$.

The results of methods (19) and (20) receiving in the application them to solve problem (21), have tabulated in table 2.

problems in a simplified form. For the demonstrating of this let us consider application method (19) and (20) to solve following problem:

Table 2.

Receiving results for step size $h = 1/32$

Step size	Variable	Error for the Simpson's method	Error for the method (20)
$h = 1/32$	1.250	0.85E-07	0.63E-09
	1.500	0.23E-05	0.10E-06
	1.750	0.60E-05	0.27E-06
	2.000	0.77E-05	0.32E-06
	1.031	0.29E-05	0.25E-07

Conclusion.

It is known that there are many papers dedicated to calculation of definite integrals. In these paper have considered for its constructed some methods or it's modification to calculation of definite integrals. It is clear that for the comparison of these methods it usually has used its exactness. Noted that in often for this aim are used the asymptotic equalities. Many specialists are using this asymptotic equalities for the sufficiently small step size. In this case the value of the computational works also increases, but in using bilateral methods such cases do not arise. Therefore here decided to recommend to use above described ways think many processes solving mathematical models, which described the investigation as the from the different fields

of natural sciences. It should be noted that the construction and application of quadrature formula is more difficult than the using of a class of methods constructed to solve the initial-value problem for the ODEs of the first order (see equalities (6) and (8)). But as was shown here, that in the classes of methods which have investigated here, there are methods with the different properties. Consequently, to apply all the methods of type (9) to calculation of defining integrals in the case $k > 3$ cannot be taken as the suitable. Here also has given the some recommendation for the application of the using here methods. The result received here is new, therefore that will be fined its followers.

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